

Assets or Liabilities? Rethinking Wealth Through Smarter Financial Choices

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One of the financial concepts that made me reflect on and reconsider my financial views was presented in the book "Rich Dad Poor Dad" by the well-known financial guru Robert Kiyosaki. According to Kiyosaki, any asset that puts money in one's pocket is a true asset, whereas anything that keeps costing one's money is a liability.

As a graduate of a management accounting course and someone who has worked in accounting and finance, such concepts may seem too controversial. According to accounting principles, houses and cars are classified as assets because they have economic value and are recorded on the balance sheet. The view promoted by Kiyosaki encouraged me to reevaluate my attitude towards owning certain items from a different perspective.

Based on my experience, owning a house entails paying for utilities, maintenance, and other expenses. Moreover, owning a car means buying fuel, paying for repairs, and maintenance. Although both items can be classified as assets under accounting principles, they also entail a consistent outflow of money. Kiyosaki's concept provided me with a breath of fresh air. Accordingly, assessing assets is based on the financial benefits they offer. For instance, owning a house and renting it can help earn money, making the house an important asset for its owner. Similarly, having a vehicle for generating business income also makes a person feel more financially comfortable and independent, since that asset pays for itself. Over time, this concept began to influence some of my financial decisions. I carefully consider when it becomes possible to buy something that could be considered an asset. In addition to stocks, bonds, and other types of securities, I became fond of purchasing land, which I considered an asset because of its value appreciation over time.

My financial decision regarding the acquisition of a brand-new electric vehicle (EV) also stemmed from this concept. Indeed, the decision was not easy, as it entailed high upfront costs, but I did in-depth research and have seen its long-term benefits. I decided that it was worth trying. Eventually, it proved to be less expensive in the long run compared with gasoline-driven cars. Moreover, it requires minimal effort and costs to maintain.

Ultimately, making a financial decision always involves taking certain amount of risk. There is no assurance that we will succeed in the future. Nevertheless, I came to realize that decisions cannot be made without considering the potential benefits or costs.

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